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INTRAVENOUS OSTEOPOROSIS MEDICATION ADHERENCE

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By

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ABSTRACT

Non-adherence to osteoporosis medications can be as high as 50%. Increasing medication adherence rates to osteoporosis drugs can ultimately reduce fragility fracture rates and decrease the financial and quality of life burdens that ensue. In 2012, specialized nurse practitioners from a southern California ambulatory care clinic of a large health care maintenance organization began ordering an annual intravenous osteoporosis medication in an attempt to increase adherence. However, there was no consistent reminder system to ensure that patients prescribed the drug were aware when subsequent doses were due.

Following a literature review, a quality improvement project began to systematize patient reminders. An electronic reminder that was already embedded in the current electronic medical record system led to the nurse practitioners using the “Remind Me” function to notify the prescriber the subsequent dose of medication was due. At the time of the patient encounter when documenting in the medical record, an electronic reminder can be sent to the nurse practitioners that will be received 1 year later. The patient can then be notified that laboratory exams are due prior to the next medication infusion. In the previous 4 years (baseline), 277 patients received the drug zoledronic acid. Of these, 227 were females; 50 were males. The majority was between 61-89 years old. Most were Caucasian (68%); 40% had already sustained a fragility fracture.

With the reminder system, the number of patients who had the osteoporosis medication ordered by nurse practitioners increased from 21% (years 2011-2013) to 54%

in 2014 ($p < .001$). The reminder function had been instituted in 91% of 2014 cases. There was a moderate positive correlation noted for patients who received a second infusion; they were more likely to have a third infusion ($r = .532, n = 48, p < .001$). The use of the reminder system is continuing to be used when nurse practitioners order the drug. It creates a more efficient mechanism than written reminders or going through lists. The reminder is sent to all nurse practitioners, and they collaborate in communicating with the patients.

The use of an electronic reminder system such as the one implemented can help to address forgetfulness, which is one of the leading causes of medication non-adherence. Nurse practitioners need to be a continued presence in investigating issues related to medication non-adherence and in developing mechanisms to assist patients in remembering to take their medications.

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BACKGROUND

Reports of osteoporotic or osteopenic fractures in the United States are about 2 million yearly. The significance of the problem is demonstrated by multiple negative outcomes including a financial burden to the country at \$19 billion (Solomon et al., 2012). There are quality of life issues that result from the disability, pain, and subsequent decline in health, which includes death.

Problem Statement

Osteoporosis is controllable, and bone strength can be increased with medications (McClung et al., 2013). However, research demonstrates that patients are often non-compliant with these medications (Reynolds et al., 2013). One of the reasons cited for non-adherence with annual intravenous (IV) bisphosphonate zoledronic acid is the lack of a system to remind the patient and the prescriber that the patient is due for a subsequent dose of the medication of (Curtis, Huifeng, Matthews, Saag, & Delzell, 2012). In one southern California clinic it was noted that there was no consistent method to identify, track, and remind patients who were due for subsequent doses of IV zoledronic acid. Upon further investigation the author consulted with colleagues to initiate a process to work towards remediation of this issue. This doctor of nursing practice (DNP) project focuses on the development of a process to increase medication adherence in regards to receiving annual IV zoledronic acid.

Pathophysiology

Osteoporosis is described as a disorder of the skeletal system in which the internal structure of the bone is compromised or “thinned,” thereby leading to the risk of low trauma fractures. Most people who are afflicted by this disease are unaware of their

significant bone loss until they sustain and suffer the consequences of an osteoporotic fracture. Recent data demonstrates around eight million females and two million males are afflicted with the disease in the United States. The risk of a post-menopausal female sustaining a fracture is approximately 53% in her lifetime and is 21% for older men (Edelstein et al., 2012). The data regarding death after a fracture is reported at 35% for those who suffer a hip fracture and approximately 8% for those who suffer a vertebral fracture. Death usually occurs within 1 year of sustaining the fracture (Solomon et al., 2010). A Canadian study demonstrated individuals 50 years of age or greater with hip or vertebral fractures were likely to expire within 5 years of sustaining the fracture regardless of gender (Ioannidis et al., 2009).

The class of medications known as bisphosphonates is used for the treatment of osteoporosis. These medications have been found to be efficacious in increasing bone mineral density (BMD) and in reducing fracture rates. These drugs decrease the functioning of bone cells called osteoclasts, thereby enabling more osteoblast formation, which increases bone cell production (McClung et al., 2013).

A large observational study examined the efficacy of two bisphosphonates. In this study, there was a 45% reduction in hip fractures in post-menopausal females on bisphosphonate treatment for 2 years (Lindsay, Watts, Lange, Delmas, & Silverman, 2013). In addition, there was a 30% reduction in non-vertebral fractures for postmenopausal women on treatment with bisphosphonates for 2 years (Lindsay et al., 2013). However, for multiple reasons many patients do not adhere to the recommended treatment regimen.

Patient Perception of Disease

There are studies that examine patient perceptions regarding their diagnosis, since most people afflicted with osteoporosis are unaware that they have the disease and the potential impact the disease has on their future health, quality of life, and independence. Edelstein et al. (2012) examined patients' perceptions regarding their diagnosis of osteoporosis using the self regulation model (SRM). According to the SRM, people have five domains that affect their ability to apprehend the significance of their disease process. These five domains encompass the patients' identity, which is how they describe, recognize, and relate to their disease based on their symptoms; the timeline of the health problem, which is the patients' understanding of the length of time they will be afflicted with the disease; the disease consequences, which is how the patients' think the disease will influence them; the cure or control of the disease, which is the patients' understanding regarding their ability to manage or treat the disease; and the cause of the illness, which is how the patient believes the disease began. The importance of understanding and acknowledging the patients' perception of the disease severity and the subsequent impact on their quality of life is extremely important since this directly affects their ability to decide to initiate and maintain treatment (Gellad, Grenard, & Marcum, 2011).

Impact of Communication and Education

It is extremely important for the patient to understand the significance of osteoporotic drug therapy and medication adherence. One of the barriers to medication adherence is the medical doctor's (MD) and/or nurse practitioner's (NP) ability to communicate the importance of drug therapy and medication adherence (Reynolds et al.,

2013). A study conducted to assess medication therapy described communication skills between the prescriber and the patient as being essential to medication adherence with osteoporotic medications (Tafaro et al., 2013). In addition, the prescriber needs to have a comprehensive knowledge of the disease process and an understanding of the significance of disease management. Another issue identified in the study was the patients' perception of their disease based on the amount of time the prescriber spent conveying the importance of disease control. Visits that were less than 10 minutes were found to be inadequate to impart this knowledge (Tafaro et al., 2013).

Osteoporosis Care as a Specialty

At Kaiser Permanente (KP) Southern California Region, these issues were addressed by having a core group of individuals educated and certified to interpret bone densities and treat patients who meet the criteria for treatment. The group called "Healthy Bones" care managers is comprised primarily of nurse practitioners (NPs) and physician assistants (PAs). At the local medical center this group is comprised of three NPs and three physician endocrinologists who oversee the process.

Identification of the Problem

Medication adherence to osteoporotic treatment has been found to be as low as 50 % 1 year after initiation of therapy (Solomon et al., 2010). In addition to the factors mentioned above, there are other issues that lead to the inability of the patient to initiate and/or continue medication therapy. Communication is one of the major issues, which requires remediation in order to improve subsequent medication adherence. The group of "Healthy Bones" care managers at the local medical center identified a communication process issue. The matter of follow up for a yearly infusion of

intravenous (IV) zoledronic was not occurring, as it should in this population. It was identified that there was no consistent system in place to notify the NP care manager that the patient was due for the subsequent doses of the drug. This became apparent to the local group of NPs because they had begun ordering the IV infusion of zoledronic acid the prior year in 2012.

The current practice recommendation is for the patient to receive the drug annually (Novartis, 2013) and then it is recommended to perform periodic repeat bone density tests to determine the effectiveness of the treatment. This is a small population of patients in this health maintenance organization (HMO) because the first line drug is an oral bisphosphonate, and the IV zoledronic acid is reserved for patients who cannot tolerate the oral form of the medication due to gastrointestinal (GI) side effects or upper GI disease processes (Kaiser Permanente, 2012).

Project Goals and Objectives

The main objective of this quality improvement project was to implement a change in provider documentation practice with the use of the EMR to increase medication adherence for subsequent doses of IV zoledronic acid, thereby decreasing fracture incidence in osteoporotic patients. The objectives of the quality improvement process change included:

1. Collaborate with Healthy Bones team members to develop a workable solution using the EMR to remind prescribers that the subsequent dose of IV zoledronic acid was due and initiation of a system to notify the patient.
2. Educate fellow team members in the process to ensure consistency.

3. Initiate the change in the documentation process with the use of the EMR that notified the prescriber that the patient was due for a subsequent dose of IV zoledronic acid 1 year later.
4. Develop a workable system with support staff to ensure the quality improvement process was utilized correctly and the patients were notified of follow up needed.
5. Develop a methodology to measure the effectiveness of the quality improvement change in the documentation process.
6. Begin a data measurement process of subsequent administered doses of IV zoledronic acid 1 year after implementation of quality improvement process to determine medication adherence and evaluate the process.
7. Use criteria from a previous study that defined being late as not receiving the subsequent dose by 18 months (Lee et al., 2012).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

There are multiple issues, which can impact the patient's ability to adhere with a prescribed medication regimen. Some issues that affect medication non-adherence can be patient related while other issues can be related to an ordering provider or a health care system. These are some of the issues which require further exploration.

Factors that Effect IV Zoledronic Acid Adherence

There are multiple problems that have been identified and contribute to IV zoledronic acid medication adherence. Lee, Nho, Ha, and Koo (2012) used a patient questionnaire to ascertain why the patients did not return for a second infusion of IV zoledronic acid. In this particular study the subsequent year follow-up medication adherence was estimated at 36%. There was a 52% response rate on the follow up questionnaire inquiring why the participant declined a second infusion. The reasons given were due to side effects, financial issues, and patient lack of knowledge regarding the disease process, importance of medication compliance, and effectiveness of medication in improving bone strength.

Curtis et al. (2012) compared medication adherence between two different IV bisphosphonates. One of the IV bisphosphonate medications, which is called ibandronate and is administered every 3 months, was compared to the yearly IV bisphosphonate zoledronic acid in terms of medication adherence. The study found that ibandronate group adherence was significantly less than the IV zoledronic acid medication adherence, which may be due to the increased frequency of ibandronate administration. In this study, the characteristics associated with decreased adherence with a second infusion of

IV zoledronic acid was older age and receiving the drug at an outpatient infusion center as compared to receiving the infusion at the prescriber's office. The issue identified in this study as well as others indicates the necessity of implementing a system to ensure that the patient is identified and notified about necessary subsequent medication dosages (Curtis et al., 2012; Vollmer et al., 2011). The data regarding non-adherence to osteoporosis medication is a large public health issue since the literature supports that being adherent to bisphosphonates will significantly reduce fragility fractures. One study concluded if osteoporosis medication adherence rates were at least 80% or greater, there could be a potential benefit of reducing fractures by 43% (Siris, Pasquale, Wang, & Watts, 2011).

Use of Electronic Notification

Some studies suggest that the use of EMR and other databases can be useful in improving medication adherence (Vollmer et al., 2011). Although the use of the EMR has been beneficial in many respects, it is limited in others. One limitation is that if the patient does not pick up a medication in the pharmacy or receive an IV medication in the KP system the ordering provider is not notified. In addition, there is no automatic electronic notification system in place in the KP system to notify the patient and/or NP care manager that the patient is due for another infusion. This is an area where the local prescribers can increase medication adherence by developing a system using the EMR to be notified that the patient is due for re-evaluation of needed laboratory exams prior to the next infusion due date and initiation of the ordering process. The overarching purpose of this scholarly project was to develop a system to ensure that patients receive

the recommended amount of yearly IV osteoporosis treatments thereby reducing the risk of osteoporotic fractures.

Theoretical Framework

Systems Research Organizing Model

The use of a theoretical framework in developing a process change is imperative. It helps those involved in the change develop a systematic method to identify all the processes and individuals involved in the problem, which helps the group move in a common direction toward consensus building and achieving a common result (Brewer, Verran, & Stichler, 2008). The systems research organizing model (SROM) has evolved out of previous theoretical frameworks to address the complex issues associated with the relationships between variables (Mitchell, Ferketich, & Jennings, 1998). It helps to define the subject of interest and can be used by different disciplines in different clinical situations. The SROM looks at all of the parts of a system and how those parts interact. There are four key constructs in the model. Using the SROM in evidence-base practice (EBP) and quality improvement is supported since the model helps those involved: understand current data on the identified issue, ensure a structure to investigate additional possible issues, and utilize the synthesis of other studies to influence practice (Brewer et al., 2008). Permission was obtained to use the theoretical framework. See Appendix A and Appendix B.

SROM Definitions

There is multidirectional interaction between the four key constructs of the SROM labeled as the “client, context, action focus, and outcomes” (Brewer et al., 2008, p. 11). In using the SROM, the investigator will need to identify which of the variables

will measure the key constructs and define them. The client construct is defined as the construct that has been considered to impact or affect the three other constructs.

Depending on the phenomena being studied, the *client* could be a person(s) or a process whereby the variables may be placed in different constructs and are considered to be interchangeable.

Context is the construct synonymous with the setting of the project. The project leader determines the context and if a change in the context is necessary to modify the expected outcome. The use of the SROM allows the context or setting to be a major issue in determining the outcome. Features of the setting have the capacity to cause change, and in this case, they may be defined as an intervention or as the action focus. The *action focus*, another construct, is described as being the construct that is subject to change, considered dynamic, can be measured, and in experimental research is the independent variable or the intervention. Team members can influence the variables in the action focus construct in their process change in order to change outcomes.

Outcomes are the construct in the SROM model, which are a result of some type of change or manipulation. The outcome(s) could be a result of the influence of other variables and can consist of varying situations. Depending on the outcome(s), additional unexpected reactions may occur in the process, which may cause reassessment of the action focus. The supplementary information obtained can be analyzed which may cause additional or different interventions to be considered to arrive at the desired outcome. Although there are different potential areas for measurement in the SROM, not all the variables or constructs need to be measured. The SROM can be customized to more

multifaceted structures, which is considered beneficial to the multifactorial changes in the health care arena (Brewer et al., 2008; see Figure 1).

SROM Literature Review

SROM use in hospital nursing surveillance. There are several studies in the literature that have used the SROM as the theoretical framework. Kelly and Vincent (2010) analyzed the theory of hospital nursing surveillance that was defined as a more complex construct than merely observing and assessing data. Complex analysis and subsequent interventions are made by surveillance techniques. In this analysis the investigators used the SROM to allow for differing influences in the system to be evaluated in order explain the outcomes. There were multiple constructs, which

Figure 1. Systems Research Organizing Model (SROM).

included nursing surveillance (action focus), patients (client), hospital characteristics, organizational characteristics or nursing units (context), and the “prevention of failure to rescue” (outcomes). The multifactorial relationships between the variables,

multidirectional interactions between constructs, and feedback methodology is inherent in using the SROM and allow the investigator to deduct more accurate conclusions regarding the relationships in the process that lead to a certain outcome(s). The researchers concluded that the use of the SROM is valuable to draw conclusions regarding more complex systems that impact patient care processes and outcomes.

SROM use in nursing home resident weight loss. Penland (2010) examined the constructs in the relationships between unintentional weight loss in nursing home residents and the nurse's knowledge of nutrition. In this study, the client was defined as the nurse, their current understanding of nutrition in this population, their educational background, and the years of experience the nurse had. The context was defined as the ownership status of the nursing home, if profit or not for profit, as this was found to have a financial effect on how well the nutrition of the residents was assessed, addressed, and maintained, and the outcome was the unintentional weight loss of the residents. In this study, as well as others, the SROM was adapted depending on the definition of the constructs and how they were applied to the SROM (Penland, 2010; Saewert, 2003).

SROM use in behavioral health. The use of the SROM was modified to include a behavioral component into the SROM model. Known as the systems research organizing model for behavioral health (SROM-BH), Saewert (2003) adapted the model to address the constructs related to delivering quality behavioral health care and the desired outcomes. The client was defined as the patient, their demographics, diagnosis, treatment, and level of care necessitated. Context was defined as the ability to access care and cost containment. Interventions, also known as the action focus in the SROM, were defined in terms of the patient's level of participation in the care and the actions or

techniques utilized. There were multiple outcomes or consequences that were measured as a result of the intervention which included quality, appropriateness, level of functioning, recovery authentication, and symptom relief. The author reports that although there were not reciprocal relationships in the SROM-BH as there are in the SROM, the use of the SROM-BH will be useful in subsequent studies (Saewert, 2003).

SROM use in informatics. Effken (2003) modified the use of the SROM to develop the informatics research organizing model (IRO). In this model adapted by the University of Arizona College of Nursing, Department of Informatics, the SROM conceptual model was merged with the systems development life cycle process model (SDLC). The key components of the SDLC are planning, analysis, design, implementation, maintenance, and at times evaluation. In this combined model the four key constructs of the SROM are maintained and defined. The client construct is defined as data and information, which is collected from customers. This includes the behaviors and characteristics unique to the consumer. The context is described as the cultural, economic, and social environments that are the setting in where the intervention transpires. Outcomes in the IRO relate to the information, actions, decisions, and knowledge obtained from the data that demonstrate improvement in cost, safety, and client satisfaction. As in the inception of the SROM, the author acknowledges the ability of the IRO to conceptualize highly complex processes and purports its use in diverse health care environments since they are highly complex and dynamic (Effken, 2003).

Application of SROM in IV Zoledronic Acid Adherence

The use of the SROM theoretical framework is appropriate for use in medication adherence. Medication ordering and ensuring delivery of the IV administration is a

complex process where many factors impact the patient's ability to be compliant with the treatment regimen. In the case of IV zoledronic acid medication adherence there are multiple factors that contribute to the non-adherence. The variables in the *client construct* are the patient, their family, and the ordering prescriber. The ability of the patient to be adherent with medication administration can be influenced depending on their age, input from family and/or friends, understanding of the disease process, treatment risks and benefits, and the relationship they have with the provider (Edelstein et al., 2012; Tafaro et al., 2013). The prescriber is the ordering NP or physician, which in the case of the Healthy Bones program ensures a certain knowledge base inherent in understanding the mechanics of the medication ordering process that includes the rationale for the use of the IV zoledronic acid, risk and benefits, potential side effects, and contraindications (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. SROM use in IV medication adherence process change.

The *context* or setting, which at first may not seem to be important in the process, is actually integral to the medication adherence. The context is the infusion clinic that is part of the closed loop system in the KP medical system. The order for the medication is placed in the medical record as well as faxed to the infusion clinic. The prescriber as well as the registered nurse (RN) administering the drug and the infusion pharmacist are part of the integrated system. The integrated system at KP contributes to medication adherence as identified in other studies where the patient was given the IV bisphosphonate at an outside facility, thereby adding another variable in the context construct that decreases the potential for medication adherence in 1 year (Curtis et al., 2012). An issue which can impact the use of this particular setting is related to the patient's ability to have transportation to the medical center where the infusion center is located, if the patient does not live in close proximity to the medical center and/or does not drive, this interferes with their ability to receive the medication.

The *action focus* for this particular process lies in the fact that there is no consistent methodology to remind the prescriber that the patient is due for the subsequent doses of medication administration. The intervention to be addressed is developing a process that is agreeable to all the members of the Healthy Bones team, increasing medication adherence, and achieving a consensual process for all involved. There were several processes in place at the time of the project implementation, which were utilized by the different prescribers, none of which ensured consistent and appropriate follow up. Although there are multiple outcomes, which can be identified from increased adherence to osteoporosis medication administration, the *desired outcome* of this process change was to increase the number of members who had the medication reordered in 1 year

through the implementation of the Remind Me function. An increase in medication adherence to IV zoledronic acid will ultimately decrease low trauma or fragility fracture rates (Lindsay et al., 2013) and help to address the associated financial costs and quality of life issues that ensue.

Literature Search

A literature search was conducted utilizing the databases: PubMed, CINAHL, and EBSCO. Search terms included: osteoporosis medication compliance, postmenopausal females, and drug therapy. Further delineation of the search included oral bisphosphonates and zoledronic acid. Limits on the search-included journals published between 2009-2014 and English language only. Other limitations included scholarly journals in endocrinology, bone mineral density, and medicine. Publications excluded from the search were those that addressed prescription drugs to treat osteoporosis other than bisphosphonates, children, and individuals with other comorbidities and medication therapies which impact bone loss.

A secondary literature search was conducted to evaluate research on using electronic medical record systems to increase medication adherence. This search was conducted utilizing the databases: PubMed, CINAHL, and EBSCO. Inclusions were publications in English. Key search terms included: medication adherence, chronic illness, technology, clinical reminders, and use of the electronic medical records. Publications excluded were those studies with children. A lower number of publications were found due to the limitations of the search terms, and publications between 2009-2014 were included.

Synthesis of Literature

According to Bonnel and Smith (2014), performing a review of the literature is an important phase of project development. Synthesis of the literature is a necessary component to assist in the development of the project. It provides an opportunity to critique current research on the topic of interest and identify parallels and inconsistencies, thereby increasing the validity of the project development (Bonnel & Smith, 2014). The synthesis of the literature regarding medication adherence supports the quality improvement process by delineating the barriers and other influences, which lead to increased medication non-adherence. Various techniques and technologies that have been found to be efficacious in increasing medication adherence will be explained. Multiple factors that include patient socio-economic status and patient perceptions, which may contribute to medication non-adherence, will be discussed.

Medication Adherence

Patients who suffer from chronic illnesses, which include osteoporosis, have been found to have a high incidence of medication non-adherence (Curtis et al., 2012; Edelstein et al., 2012; Solomon et al., 2012). The burden of chronic illness in our country is increasing as the population ages and therefore medication non-adherence must be addressed. Iuga and McGuire (2014) noted that approximately 10% of hospitalization rates in the elderly are due to medication non-adherence. The costs for non-adherence to chronic illness medication use have been estimated to be between \$100-300 billion in the United States (Iuga & McGuire, 2014).

There are inconsistent definitions of medication adherence, which complicates studying the phenomenon. One explanation by Cramer et al. (2008) described adherence

as having two factors: persistence and compliance. Compliance is “the extent to which a patient acts in accordance with the prescribed interval and dose of a dosing regimen” (p. 46). Persistence is described as “the length of time from initiation to discontinuation of therapy” (p. 46).

Patient Determinants of Medication Adherence

Kardas, Lewek, and Matyjaszczyk (2013) reported that there are constructs of patient adherence, which include “initiation, implementation, and discontinuation” (p. 1). The World Health Organization recommends further examination of the concepts of medication adherence, which include “socioeconomic factors, healthcare team and system-related factors, condition-related factors, therapy-related factors, and patient-related factors” (as cited in Kardas et al., 2013, p. 1). In this systematic review, 771 individual issues were identified that impact medication adherence. Some of the most common patient determinants of medication adherence that were found to be important included a supportive social environment and daily dosing as opposed to twice a day or more frequent dosing. Older individuals as well as those with a higher socio-economic status (SES) were found to have increased adherence with taking medications (Kardas et al., 2013). If patients suffer adverse side effects to the medicine, have several medical comorbidities, and require several medications daily, these factors as well have been found to contribute to medication non-adherence (Tafaro et al., 2013). A systematic review of medication adherence in the elderly population found similar results regarding determinants of medication adherence. Individuals diagnosed with several different disease processes and taking increased amounts of prescription medications led to an increase in medication non-adherence (Gellad et al., 2011).

Forgetfulness in Medication Adherence

A study that focused on older patients' beliefs related to medication adherence found that the population of individuals 65 years of age and older have some of the highest rates of medication non-adherence, reported as approximately 50% (Sirey, Greenfield, Weinberger, & Bruce, 2013). The authors reported the most common reason given for medication non-adherence was forgetfulness; however non-adherence was not increased with a diagnosis of cognitive disability (Sirey et al., 2013). A similar study focused on adult self-reported reasons for medication non-adherence, which also described forgetfulness as the most common reason provided for not taking medications regularly (Boskovic, Leppee, Culig, & Eric, 2013). This is an important factor to address since most of the common barriers to medication non-adherence are related to the patients' own influences (Boskovic et al., 2013).

Patient Barriers

There are multiple actual or perceived patient barriers which have been found to impact a patient's ability to be adherent with their medication regimen. Although adequate social support such as family support and ability to pay for medications has a positive effect on medication adherence, the actual reasons for lack of social support are not as well defined (Kardas et al., 2013). Having emotional and family support in the form of financial help or the ability of the family to be cohesive was found to be an important determinant, which led to increase medication adherence (Kardas et al., 2013). The authors also discussed the potential of social stigma with certain diseases and the impact on medication adherence. These findings were more prominent in medication

non-adherence as in the case of a potentially communicable disease such as human immunodeficiency virus or tuberculosis (Kardas et al., 2013).

Other significant patient barriers to medication adherence included those patients with psychiatric diagnoses as well as those with drug and alcohol addictions who have also been found to have lower rates of medication adherence (Kardas et al., 2013; Sirey et al., 2013). Tafaro et al. (2013) reported that when the patient has an asymptomatic condition or feels better and their perception is that the medicine is not needed then they are less likely to take it.

Impact of Disease Diagnosis on Medication Adherence

A large integrated health care organization evaluated medication adherence of patients with eight different chronic illnesses. Those that had the best adherence were: hypertension, hyperlipidemia, osteoporosis, multiple sclerosis, and cancer patients. These conditions were reported to have about 75% medication adherence, while patients with diabetes, asthma, and depression had significantly lower adherence rates. The data was obtained from electronic medical records using patient demographics and medication possession ratios (MPR). As in other studies mentioned, this study also found lower medication adherence rates with lower SES, multiple drugs, dosing multiple times daily, multiple chronic conditions, and in minorities (Rolnick, Pawloski, Hedblom, Asche, & Bruzek, 2012).

Provider-Patient Interactions

There are other barriers that may be actual or perceived by the patient, which decreases their ability to start or take their medications regularly. Patients may not understand the consequences of deciding against treating their disease. Some individuals

do not comprehend the positive effects of treatment or may have received conflicting information regarding the medication effects and or side effects from different medical providers (Kardas et al., 2013). There may be mistrust by the patient, significant other, or family member with a medical provider or healthcare organization (Kardas et al., 2013). If there is not an established relationship between the patients, their family or significant other with the medical provider the patients are less likely to agree to treatment (Edelstein et al., 2012; Gellad et al., 2011; Kardas et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2012; Sirey et al., 2013; Tafaro et al., 2013).

Nurse Practitioner Versus Physician Prescriber

No literature was located demonstrating differences between patient medication non-adherence based on whether a physician or a nurse practitioner ordered the medication. However, a recent systematic review validated the use of NPs in providing quality care; a review of 63 studies demonstrated that the outcomes of care being provided by NPs as being equivalent to physicians in measures of safety, excellence, and efficiency (Stanik-Hutt et al., 2013). In the case of lipid management, the outcomes were better in NP provided care as compared to care involving physicians only (Stanik-Hutt et al., 2013).

In a study by Jessee and Rutledge (2012) nurse practitioner coordinated group visits when compared to routine primary care provider visits demonstrated improved blood sugar readings, patients reported a better understanding of their disease management, and increased self confidence in self-care techniques. Gilbert and Hayes (2009) reported that older patients were satisfied in general with their clinic visit with an NP and were likely to follow the recommendations made by the NP in regards to medical

information. However studies have found that the patients who were given lifestyle information were less likely to follow those recommendations (Gilbert & Hayes, 2009; Hayes, 2007).

The Socio-Economic Burdens of Osteoporosis

Increase in Mortality

The issue of increased mortality is very dramatic and of great concern in those afflicted with osteoporosis and who have sustained a fracture. A large prospective study of females who suffered from hip fractures found that 17% of the patients who sustained a hip fracture did not survive longer than 1 year after the surgery, which was twice the number of people in the non-fracture control group. Most of the deaths occurred in the first 3 months following the surgery. In addition 48% of the hip fracture patients were deceased within 14 years after the fracture (LeBlanc et al., 2011). A study in Denmark demonstrated that that the mortality rates following hip fracture within the first year after fracture was 37% for men and 27% for women. The authors of this study attributed the increased mortality rate in males from data that suggests the men had less diagnosed or unknown chronic illnesses as compared to their female counterparts and therefore were not being treated for these illnesses which lead to an increase in medical complications (Kannegaard, Van der Mark, Eiken, & Abrahamsen, 2010).

A study that evaluated the risk of subsequent fractures found that 30% of females and 22% of males experienced another fracture within approximately 5 years of the first fracture and this increased the mortality rate for this group by 49% in females and 74% in males (Bliuc et al., 2009). A systematic review reported similar findings, that men in

general have approximately twice the risk of death than women following hip fractures (Abrahamsen, van Staa, Ariely, Olson, & Cooper, 2009).

Financial Burden

The financial implications and the resultant outcomes for those who suffer a fragility fracture are staggering. Blume and Curtis (2011) analyzed the financial costs of fractures per event to be \$8,600 on average per episode and up to \$10,800. If the individual has other comorbidities the cost goes up by \$4,400 per illness. If the patient has cancer or Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) diagnoses, the additional financial burden can be as high as 2-3 times greater than the \$4,400. According to Ioannidis et al. (2013), the majority of osteoporotic fractures occurred in the 65-84 year old age group. The average hospital stay for hip fractures is about 13 days. The total number of hospitalized days was higher for those afflicted with non-hip and non-vertebral fractures, about 3 times higher than hip fractures. This was similar when the length of stay was analyzed for patients who required additional hospitalization in long term care facilities after the acute care hospitalizations. In this large international study, 93% of the fractures reported were non-hip fractures and as a result the majority of the costs associated with low trauma fractures were in this population. Additionally, if the patient had a prior fracture, this contributed to a longer hospitalization (Ioannidis et al., 2013).

A study by Pike et al. (2011) demonstrated in the second year after treatment for the original fracture, costs incurred for caring for patients with pelvic fractures was greatest at \$5,121, hip fractures at \$3,930, femur fractures at \$3,828, and non-vertebral fractures were \$2,072. The types of medical care which were included in the cost

analysis differentiated the areas where direct patient care took place if it was inpatient, outpatient, in an emergency room and/or long term care; the number of days the patient was hospitalized or the number of out patient visits; the types of services required such as rehabilitation, radiology or specialty care; the types of fractures that were sustained such as femur, upper extremity, lower extremity, pelvic, rib or multiple fractures; the types of drugs utilized considered fracture related such as pain medications or antibiotics, osteoporosis treatment drugs, or any other type of drug therapy required in the second year after the fracture.

Burge, King, Balda, and Worley (2003) reviewed data for the cost of osteoporotic care in 2000 and used a statistical analysis program to predict the cost of osteoporotic care in the year 2025. In the state of Florida alone the anticipated costs of caring for osteoporotic fractures will increase almost 60%. Reducing the financial burden of caring for osteoporotic fractures is another area whereby NPs can improve the current health care system by increasing medication adherence rates for patients with osteoporosis and therefore impacting health care costs in this population.

Impact on Quality of Life

There are studies that assess the quality of life (QOL) in individuals with significant bone loss as well as those who have already suffered a fragility fracture. Being treated for bone loss in general has been shown to improve health related quality of life (HRQOL) indicators for patients who were treated with either IV zoledronic acid or the oral bisphosphonate alendronate. Hadji et al. (2012) reported that patients who received either the IV zoledronic acid or oral alendronate reported the largest subjective improvements in pain control. If the patient had suffered a fracture and had received IV

zoledronic acid, they reported an overall improvement in all HRQOL indicators between the first assessment and the subsequent assessment in 12 months (Hadji et al., 2012).

A study by Silverman et al. (2012) demonstrated that women with clinical fractures reported a statistically significant negative change in their HRQOL from baseline up to 36 months after their fracture. The most significant findings were in functional decline, adverse psychological issues, and suffering from persistent pain (Silverman et al., 2012). An international study by Borgström et al. (2013) noted similar findings in that HRQOL measures significantly declined after an individual sustained an osteoporotic fracture. In addition if the patient had a higher HRQOL measurement before the fracture, the patient reported an even larger loss in HRQOL measurements post fracture. Those individuals who were hospitalized had an even greater loss of HRQOL measurements (Borgström et al., 2013).

Use of Technology in Medication Adherence

With the increased use of technology in healthcare organizations as well as use in patients' homes, comes an abundance of ways to communicate with patients and/or their families. There are studies that examine the use of electronic reminders at the time of the visit. The primary intended use is to increase recommended cancer screenings, osteoporosis screenings, administration of needed vaccinations, increase hypertension control, diabetes control, and other outcome measures that indicate quality healthcare is being provided (Holt, Thorogood, & Griffiths, 2012). In addition the electronic prescribing systems have been found to increase medication adherence by 10% (Iuga & McGuire, 2014).

Clinical Encounter Reminders

A systematic review and meta-analysis by Holt et al. (2012) of 42 studies demonstrated the efficacy of the use of clinical reminders at the time of the clinical encounter. The use of the reminder function is to increase necessary clinical interventions and produce significant changes in patient outcomes. The authors reported some issues that needed to be addressed to successfully implement a reminder system, these should include: an automated computer based decision support at the time of decision making, a discussion regarding importance of the intervention to the patient and or provider, assessment of cost-effectiveness of the intervention, the user-friendliness of the system, and the amount time necessitated to complete the intervention at the visit (Holt et al., 2012).

A smaller study in Kodiak, Alaska in a primary care setting demonstrated an increase in screenings for depression, smoking cessation, partner violence, alcohol abuse, cardio-vascular disease, and preventative health care screenings with the implementation of a reminder function at the time of the visit (Onders, Spillane, Reilley, & Leston, 2013). The authors reported the success of their project was due to ongoing feedback from staff and providers, using an ongoing quality improvement process, and delegating the clinical reminder function to support staff. They also recommend having the reminder function in a specific location in the electronic medical record, which facilitated the use of the function.

Lessons Learned

There are not always consistent positive outcomes with the implementation of EMR reminders in health care organizations. Another primary care study associated

with a large academic medical center in the United States did not find improvements in the implementation of patient reminders for use in intensifying screening rates for mammography, bone density measurements, and for cholesterol and hemoglobin A1c testing in diabetics (El-Kareh et al., 2011). The authors however acknowledged the difficulties that contributed to the failure of a successful implementation of the reminder function. When the authors sought feedback from the users they discovered the difficulties were due to the failure to educate and engage the providers in the use of the system during the implementation phase. In addition, they found there were workflow inefficiency issues and multiple inaccuracies in the reminders that led to extra time and effort. The authors concluded that the use of provider and staff feedback in the beginning of the system implementation would have promoted re-evaluation, prompted changes, and subsequently increased use of the reminder functions (El-Kareh et al., 2011).

Use of Text Messaging in Medication Adherence

There is an increased use of technology in other patient reminder systems. A randomized control trial (RCT) of patients discharged after cardiac interventions implemented the use of text messaging. After discharge, patients were randomized into intervention and control groups. Patients were sent either a message that included education, a message that included medication reminders and education, or patients were randomized to a control group, which did not receive any text messaging. The authors reported both types of text messaging were found to be effective in increasing medication adherence with antiplatelet therapy (Park, Howie-Esquivel, Chung, & Dracup, 2013).

A large (RCT) in China implemented the use of text messaging for medication adherence. The first message sent was educational and included a reminder to take the medication. Subsequent messages sent were simple reminders to help patients remember to take their medications. The intervention was significant in reducing missed or delayed dosages and medication adherence was increased. The use of this technology was found to be more effective in the 20-34 year old group as compared to participants' ≥ 65 years old (Huang et al., 2013). When attempting to increase medication adherence rates, the age of the patient should be considered in implementing this type of technology.

Conclusions From Literature Synthesis

The literature review supports the use of the electronic medical record and some type of electronic reminder system to increase patient adherence to recommended medical screenings and treatments (Holt et al., 2012; Onders et al., 2013). The type of electronic reminder system implemented should be congruent with the age of the patient (Huang et al., 2013). Tackling the multi-factorial issues with medication non-adherence will continue to be a challenge and therefore the barriers, which are considered to be modifiable, such as addressing forgetfulness, can be facilitated by the use of an electronic system (Boskovic et al., 2013; Sirey et al., 2013).

The burden of chronic illness to this country will continue to grow as the population ages and with aging comes the financial burden of caring for this population. One third of people ≥ 65 years old have fallen; this has become one of the leading causes of death from injury (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2013a). In the year 2030 people 65 years of age and greater will comprise 20% of the United States

population. Ninety-five percent of health care dollars spent on this population is related to caring for chronic disease (CDC, 2013b). It is imperative to address the issue of medication adherence in this population. Specifically, this quality improvement project addressed one of the potential medication adherence issues when ordering IV zoledronic acid with the implementation of the Remind Me function.

METHODS

Setting

The quality improvement project took place at Kaiser Permanente's Panorama City Medical Center (PCMC) and Santa Clarita Medical Office Building with the use of the electronic medical record (EMR) Remind Me function. Three endocrinologists and three Healthy Bones NPs routinely write the prescriptions for IV zoledronic acid. There is an on-site medical center infusion clinic with a pharmacist who reviews the orders and dispenses the drug. Registered Nurses (RN) administer and monitor the patients while they receive the drug. Currently the orders are faxed to the infusion clinic in addition to being placed in the EMR.

Sample

Inclusion criteria for the project included all patients who have had IV zoledronic acid ordered in the last 4 years, and were either female and post-menopausal with the diagnosis of osteoporosis or osteopenia with higher fracture risk, or men who were 50 year of age or older with the diagnosis of osteoporosis or osteopenia with higher fracture risk. Exclusion criteria for the project included males less than 50 years old, females less than 50 years old or not menopausal, and individuals with a diagnosis other than osteoporosis for which they received the IV zoledronic acid.

Ethical Issues

Full disclosure of the change in documentation practice and explanation of the quality improvement data extraction process was given to the members of the local Healthy Bones team who routinely order IV zoledronic acid in the PCMC service area. The prescribers' participation was not mandatory but was requested. During data

extraction neither individual patients nor prescribers were independently identified to ensure that data confidentiality was maintained. The author who is an employee of the organization completed the data extraction and evaluation.

An Institutional Review Board (IRB) application was submitted to the Kaiser Permanente (KPSC) Southern California IRB. Upon IRB review it was determined that the IV zoledronic acid quality improvement (QI) project did not constitute a human subject research study. See Appendix C. Subsequently the KPSC IRB determination was submitted to the California State University at Los Angeles (CSULA) IRB. Following review, the CSULA IRB accepted the KP determination that IRB approval was not required. See Appendix D.

Planning the Quality Improvement Program

The change in documentation process in the electronic medical record (EMR) was recommended by the infusion pharmacists at the PCMC based on their practice to ensure members who need subsequent infusions of other intravenous medications were notified to return to the infusion clinic for further treatments. The use of the Remind Me function in the electronic medical record was used successfully in the infusion pharmacists' practice. When the change in practice to initiate the use of the Remind Me function was instituted there was no consistent methodology in place to notify the NP prescriber that in the following year the patient was due for the IV zoledronic acid medication administration once again. The author collaborated with the Healthy Bones team at the PCMC service area by performing education and communicating on an ongoing basis as needed to implement the quality improvement process. The additional

steps of the documentation process the prescriber performed while in the patient's medical record included:

1. Click the "Remind Me" tab at the top right hand side of the screen.
2. Enter the reminder note and forward it to the other Healthy Bones NPs.
3. Place the patient's name and medical record number automatically when in the patients' medical record.
4. Document Reclast (zoledronic acid) follow up in the body of the message, "Notes".
5. Change the date of the message. Click on "Due date" and change the date of the message encounter to receive the notification one year later.
6. Click on the "Accept" tab to perform the last step in the "Remind Me" documentation process.

When the message comes into the Healthy Bones Pool in 1 year, the Healthy Bones NP team is notified the patient is due for the subsequent dose of medication. The prescriber reviews the chart, orders necessary laboratory exams, and the member is notified.

Methods of Evaluation

A retrospective chart audit was done to determine the number of individuals who had received IV zoledronic acid in the previous 4 years as well as compliance with subsequent doses of the medication. The EMR review began 6 months after project implementation to determine compliance with the Remind Me function. The data review and collection continued for 10 months after the implementation of the Remind Me function.

First, a list was generated from the pharmacy that included the members who had the medication administered in the PCMC service area infusion clinic in the previous 3-year period. A retrospective quantitative chart review was done on patients who had the drug ordered previously and the Remind Me function was instituted for all applicable patients by the author. The author performed the chart review and data collection, thus no additional training was required.

The patient demographic data that was collected included: age, race, gender, and if a history of a low trauma fracture occurred. Other data collected included if the second and/or third doses were not received within 18 months of the previous dose, which was considered late, if the prescriber was a NP or physician, and if the patient was notified to follow up by a letter. If the patient was late for the dose, the reason for the delay if found was noted. The following issues were noted in the data collection process as reasons for being late: (a) not aware subsequent dose was due, (b) side effects were not tolerated, (c) subsequent dose not indicated per prescriber, (d) the patient had died, (e) a decrease in kidney function had occurred, (f) there was a change in the patients' health status, (g) there was a change in living situation which may have been moving out of the area or to long term care, (h) the prescriber changed the medication for bone loss, or (i) the patient was not responding to written communication for follow up. At the time of the data collection it was also noted if the patient was not late or they had received the medication on time; this was coded not applicable for being late.

The use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS™) Version 21.0 electronic software was employed to analyze the collected data. There were a total of 277 cases reviewed in the previous years including 2011-2014.

Data Analysis

The total sample size consisted of 277 patients who received the IV zoledronic acid in the time period of January 2011 through November 10, 2014. Excluded from the analysis were males less than 50 years old, females less than 50 years old or not menopausal, and individuals with a diagnosis other than osteoporosis for which they received the IV zoledronic acid such as Paget's disease. Only five individuals were excluded.

Use of descriptive statistics was employed to look at patient demographics, reasons for being late in receiving the drug, data regarding the use of the reminder function, and if the prescriber was a physician or a NP. In addition correlational analysis were used to determine if there was a difference between physician and NP prescribers in relation to non-adherence with the second and/or third doses of IV zoledronic acid. A chi-square test of independence was used to determine if there was a statistically significant increase in medication adherence at the completion of the data collection and if there was a statistically significant increase in IV zoledronic prescriptions by the NPs.

RESULTS

Demographics

As seen in Table 1, the majority of individuals receiving IV zoledronic acid were female, comprising 82% of the cases.

Table 1

Gender of Cases

Gender	<i>n</i>	%
Female	227	82
Male	50	18
Total	277	100

Table 2 shows that individuals ranged in age from 50 years to greater than 90 years of age. The greatest percentages of cases were in the 71-80 years of age category, which was 41% of the project cases. The next two most prevalent age groups were 61-70 years of age and 81-90 years of age comprising 24% and 21% of the sample respectively.

Table 2

Ages of Cases

Age	<i>n</i>	%
50-60	29	11
61-70	67	24
71-80	115	41
81-89	57	21
≥ 90	9	3
Total	277	

Racial and ethnic background was gathered from the electronic medical record.

As shown in Table 3, 68% of the sample was Caucasian. Hispanic and Asians were the

next most frequent ethnicities/race selected at 14% and 13% respectively. There were five patients, accounting for 2%, who self-identified as Middle Eastern. When the patients' race was not documented in the demographics section of the patient medical record or if it was coded "unknown," this accounted for 9 cases or 3% of the sample.

Table 3

Race of Cases

Race	<i>n</i>	%
Caucasian	188	68
Asian	35	13
Hispanic	40	14
Middle Eastern	5	2
Unknown/other	9	3
Total	277	100

A fragility or low trauma fracture is "a fall from the standing height or an impression of an inadequate trauma" which resulted in a fracture (Chevalley, Hoffmeyer Bonjour, & Rizzoli, 2002 p. 451). The EMR was examined for documentation of a fragility fracture. In the event that none was documented, the case was coded as not having a fracture. As shown in Table 4, the data reviewed between 2011-2014 demonstrated that in 40% of the cases the patient had suffered a fragility fracture.

Table 4

Incidence of Fragility Fractures

Fracture History	<i>n</i>	%
Yes	112	40
No	165	60
Total	277	100

Reasons for Not Receiving the Medication

Although IV zoledronic acid is normally prescribed in 12 month intervals, individuals in this project were not considered as “late” until the time since last infusion was 18 months or greater. This definition was adapted from research conducted by Lee et al. (2012). Data was collected to determine the reasons that patients were late for IV zoledronic acid.

Specific causes were determined by chart review and/or dialogue with patients or families. Categories included: not ordered by the prescriber due to a drug holiday or change in medication, health issues that precluded another dose, side effects that were not tolerated, no longer a Kaiser Permanente member or moved out of the service area, decrease in kidney function, death, and changes in living situation. Of special interest were those not receiving IV zoledronic acid because they were not aware it was due.

Table 5 elucidates the reasoning for not receiving subsequent doses of IV zoledronic acid in the time period 2011-2013. This review consisted of 185 cases. Of those cases the most frequent reason cited for being late was “not applicable.” Included in this category was (a) the medication was not yet due, (b) per prescriber the medication was not indicated at this time. Other cases were determined to be late because they were no longer receiving care at this Kaiser facility or exclusions because of health related issues. Twenty-two cases or 12% of the sample were determined to be unaware that the medication was due.

Implementation of the Remind Me Function

The project author instituted the Remind Me function retrospectively for all applicable cases in the 2011-2013 timeframe. As seen in Table 6, at the time of the

Table 5

Reasons Drug Not Received on Time 2011-2013

Reason drug not received on time	<i>n</i>	%
Patient not aware it was due	22	12.0
Side effects not tolerated	7	4.0
Not indicated per ordering provider	16	8.5
Deceased	16	8.5
Out of area or nonmember	2	1.0
Decrease in kidney function	3	1.0
Other health issues	8	4.0
Change in living situation or transportation issues	2	1.0
Not applicable	94	51.0
Not responding to provider/staff communication	11	6.0
Change in medication	5	3.0
Total	185	100.0

Table 6

Remind Me Function 2011-2013

Function instituted	<i>n</i>	%
Yes	47	25
No	44	24
Not applicable	94	51
Total	185	100

initial retrospective chart review, 44 cases or 24% did not have the Remind Me function instituted. The Remind Me function was implemented towards the end of the year 2013. The cases that were not candidates to receive the subsequent dose of the drug were coded as not applicable.

Cases from 2014 were reviewed for the use of the Remind Me function. As noted in Table 7, of the possible 92 cases, 84 or 91% had the Remind Me function instituted in 2014. This was an improvement when compared to the previous years

between 2011 through 2013 in which the Remind Me function was initiated only 25% of the time.

Table 7

Remind Me Function 2014

Remind Me function instituted	<i>n</i>	%
Yes	84	91.0
No	4	4.5
Not applicable	4	4.5
Total	92	100.0

During the period of data collection, specifically the time frame between the initiation of the Remind Me system and the completion of data collection process, there were insufficient data available to determine if the process had significantly improved subsequent ordering, dosing, and patients being administered zoledronic acid.

Prescribing Patterns

Prescribers were not individually identified but were classified as either physician (endocrinologist or primary care physician) or nurse practitioner. Local endocrinologists and Healthy Bones NPs prescribed the majority of IV zoledronic acid. There were five instances when a primary care physician ordered the drug. As noted in Table 8, in the 2011-2013 time period 79% of the IV zoledronic acid orders were completed by the physicians.

This was significantly different in 2014 as shown in Table 9, where 54% of the medication was ordered by the Healthy Bones nurse practitioner.

Table 8

Percentage of IV Zoledronic Acid Orders 2011-2013

Ordering provider	<i>n</i>	%
NP	39	21
Physician	146	79
Total	185	100

Table 9

Percentage of IV Zoledronic Acid Orders 2014

Ordering provider	<i>n</i>	%
NP	50	54
Physician	42	46
Total	92	100

A chi-square test of independence revealed a statistically significant increase in the proportion of NP prescribers from the 2011-2013 time period which was prior to the institution of the Remind Me intervention ($n = 39, 21.1\%$) compared to 2014 which was post institution of the Remind Me function ($n = 50, 54.3\%$; $X^2(1) = 31.18, p < .001$).

Correlational Analysis

The data demonstrated that the sample was fairly compliant with receiving the third dose of medication if the second medication was received. A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was calculated to evaluate the association between receiving the 2nd and 3rd doses of medication. A moderate positive correlation was found between receiving the 2nd and 3rd doses of IV zoledronic acid ($r = .532, n = 48, p = < .001$).

A moderate positive correlation was found between the use of the Remind Me function and receiving the 2nd and 3rd dose as shown in Table 10.

Table 10

Increase in Remind Me Function Use

Pearson product moment correlation coefficient	<i>n</i>	<i>p</i>
2nd dose $r = .503$	118	< .001
3rd dose $r = .394$	48	< .001

There were no significant correlations found between being late for receiving the drug and if the prescriber was a NP or a physician. There were no significant correlations between age, race, gender, history of a previous fracture, and IV zoledronic medication adherence.

DISCUSSION

The results of this quality improvement project demonstrate that there are multiple barriers to medication adherence for both the patient and the prescribing provider that contributed to medication non-adherence to the IV zoledronic acid annual infusion among these cases. Of particular interest are the barriers that can be eliminated through a simple, cost effective method such as the use of the Remind Me function in the EMR. In the initial data collection and analysis, the use of the Remind Me function is proving to be a valuable tool. The use of the Remind Me function and the NP prescribers' ability to help this population can directly affect health care costs, decrease morbidity and mortality rates, and help the aging population in maintaining a certain quality of life for a longer period of time.

Effectiveness of NP Prescribers

An interesting finding in the data is that there were no statistically significant differences in medication adherence with IV zoledronic acid prescriptions between the NP and physician prescribers. In the year 2014 the amount of IV zoledronic acid prescriptions written by NPs increased to 54% of the total prescriptions written and received for this drug as compared to the 2011-2013 time frame when only 21% of the prescriptions for IV zoledronic acid were written by the NPs. This data is important in justifying the use of the Healthy Bones NPs in providing this type of care.

These findings are congruent with several studies, which examined the use of NPs in managed care. Hayes (2007) examined the use NPs in managed care and found that most patients discovered communications with NPs to be very satisfying, patients

were agreeable to the proposed plan of care, the respondents wanted to see the NP at subsequent visits, and referred the NPs to their relatives and acquaintances.

Medication Adherence

There are conflicting data regarding older patients and medication adherence when looking at age as a variable (Kardas et al., 2013; Sirey et al., 2013). Being forgetful, as one grows older is common and has been found to be one of the highest reported reasons for medication non-adherence (Boskovic et al., 2013). The elderly generation of patients in general is not as technologically savvy in which case the use of electronic reminders directly to the patient may not be effective (Huang et al., 2013). The NP with the increased use of the Remind Me function at the time of the current encounter will address one of the most common reported barriers to medication adherence, which is forgetfulness with the implementation of the Remind Me function.

In addition to the above barriers to patient medication non-adherence is that many patients still do not trust health care providers (Iversen, Vora, Servi, & Solomon, 2011; Kardas et al., 2013). The Healthy Bones NP team is working together and providing consistent information that addresses the issue of receiving conflicting information, which has also been identified as a barrier to medication adherence (Iversen et al., 2011; Kardas et al., 2013). Being able to develop a relationship with the patient and their significant others can increase medication adherence because the lack of trust and not knowing the provider have been found to have a negative effect on medication adherence (Edelstein et al., 2012; Gellad et al., 2011; Kardas et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2012; Sirey et al., 2013; Tafaro et al., 2013).

Working as a team in a specialty area and communicating regularly the NPs are poised to improve medication adherence. At the time of the visit or on a phone call follow up the patients are given time to ask questions regarding test results, diagnosis, risk for fracture, and an explanation of potential risks versus benefits of receiving treatment. A direct number to reach and or leave a message for the Healthy Bones team is given and the team works together to meet the needs of this population as evidenced by the increased use of the Remind Me function.

Implications of IV Zoledronic Medication Non-Adherence

Financial Considerations

The majority of patients being treated for osteoporosis in this quality improvement project were in the 71-80 year old group range. This is an important factor to consider because as patients age and have more co-morbid chronic illnesses they may suffer decreased ability to function physically and emotionally and therefore the costs for their health care will increase significantly as well (Blume & Curtis, 2011; Ioannidis et al., 2013).

In the project sample for the years 2011-2013 there were 22 patients who were not aware they were due for their subsequent infusion. If these patients sustained an osteoporotic fracture the total costs incurred in the first year for these patients is estimated to be \$213,400 (Blume & Curtis, 2011). According to the data of Pike et al. (2011) the average medical costs post fracture in the subsequent year for these patients could be estimated at approximately \$82,230. This is a potential significant cost savings specifically if this number of untreated patients is multiplied across the all the facilities in the KP Southern California Region. If the other facilities do not institute the use of

the NPs prescribing and following up on this population, there is the potential for more patients with low trauma fractures necessitating additional treatment and in turn increasing the cost of care in this population.

Increased Mortality

Ioannidis et al. (2009) found that individuals who sustained either a hip or vertebral fracture had increased mortality rates in the first 5 years post fracture. Patients who had a hip fracture were found to have a progressive decline in their health status eventually leading to death. A very concerning issue is if an individual suffered a vertebral fracture, this was found to be a direct prognosticator of death. In this study there were no significant differences between mortality rates in males and females (Ioannidis et al., 2009). The issues with mortality in this population can be significantly decreased since the data on the efficacy of IV zoledronic acid post any type of fracture has been found to decrease the risk of a subsequent fracture by 35% (Maricic, 2010). This is another area where the use of reminder systems for medication adherence and electronic notification of fractures to the Healthy Bones care managers can make a monumental impact on the mortality rates in this population.

Impact on Quality of Life Issues

Multiple studies document the impact of QOL changes post fracture related to pain, sustaining additional osteoporotic fractures, loss of function, and fear of falling (Guillemin et al., 2014; Iversen et al., 2011; Yoon et al., 2014). In this DNP quality improvement project 40% or 112 individuals of the sample size had sustained a previous fracture. This constitutes a significant number of people who most likely experienced a negative change in their QOL indicators post fracture. In addition the quality

improvement sample consisted of 277 people who had received the IV zoledronic acid for bone loss. The Healthy Bones NPs are making a significant contribution to this population by being able to increase medication adherence to IV zoledronic acid thereby reducing the risk of fractures, improving pain, and hopefully improving QOL indicators.

Limitations

The demographics of the patients who have received the drug may not be indicative of the population the PCMC service area supports. This project captures only those individuals who have received the drug and not those who declined treatment due to various issues, including those who may not understand the gravity of the illness, potential financial implications, and QOL issues.

The NPs in the service area were the only providers who implemented the Remind Me function. There is still another subset of the population who may need to be reminded that their medications are due and there is not a consistent effective mechanism in place to remedy this. In addition there are members for whom the medication was ordered and there is no current mechanism in place for the Healthy Bones NPs to be notified when the patient does not follow up to receive their medication as ordered and discussed. This issue is currently being addressed by the RN infusion clinic staff by providing this information to the Healthy Bones staff when either the patient does not show up for the scheduled appointment at the infusion clinic or the patient is not responding to calls to schedule them for the appointment.

Finally, the time between the quality improvement project implementation to the time that the follow up chart review occurred, there were not enough patients who were due for follow up infusions to note a significant statistical difference in medication

adherence. Thus no significant outcome data was available to evaluate this aspect of the quality improvement program.

Implications for Further Studies

There are many implications for further studies or projects.

1. NPs in specialty care areas will impact health care outcomes positively and this can be demonstrated by ongoing chart review in the entire Southern California Kaiser Permanente Medical System.
2. The author will continue the data collection for 24-30 months post implementation of the “Remind Me” function. The retrospective review will determine the efficacy of the Quality Improvement Project at the PCMC.
3. The staff will track members who decline treatment to ensure follow up in subsequent years. This additional information will contribute to data on understanding medication non-adherence.
4. Healthy Bones NPs will consider the implementation of a HRQOL questionnaire to ascertain an osteoporotic individual’s quality of life. This will help to increase insight into the management of this complex population.

Conclusions

This DNP project demonstrates that nurse practitioners are a valuable part of the health care team. The Healthy Bones NPs identified a communication issue, which could contribute to medication non-adherence and collaborated in implementing a process, which was cost effective and efficient by implementing the Remind Me function. In addition, by increasing the numbers of osteoporotic patients that are seen

and treated by the Healthy Bones NPs, the endocrinologists will have more appointments for more complex osteoporotic patients who may not be candidates for zoledronic acid.

The data demonstrated to date by this DNP project is congruent with the recommendations by the Committee on the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation Initiative on the Future of Nursing at the Institute of Medicine (IOM; 2010), which addresses the issue of 32 million Americans being able to have access to health care (IOM, 2010). The use of advanced practice nurses such as specialized nurse practitioners can address the ability of Americans having access to expert affordable health care. Registered nurses (RNs) are the largest number of health care providers in the United States constituting greater than 3 million individuals (IOM, 2010). The ability to use advanced practice nurses such as NPs in delivering health care will improve access to care and as demonstrated in previous studies will help improve health care outcomes (Stanik-Hutt et al., 2013).

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APPENDIX A**LETTER SUBMITTED FOR USE OF THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK**

Colleen Bogdanich
Address, City, ST Zip
Phone: xxx-xxx-xxxx
E-Mail: cdbogdanich@csu.fullerton.edu

Date: 5/18/14

Barbara B. Brewer PhD, RN, MALS, MBA

College of Nursing
The University of Arizona
PO Box 210203
1151 S. Forest Ave
Tempe, AZ 85281

Dear Dr Brewer,

I am a doctor of nursing practice student in the Southern California CSU DNP Consortium. I am working on my capstone project. It is a quality improvement project to increase medication adherence with an intravenous osteoporosis medication. I would like to obtain your permission to use the Systems Research Organizing Model for my theoretical framework. I would appreciate your response at your earliest opportunity.

Sincerely,

Colleen Bogdanich

APPENDIX B

APPROVAL TO USE SROM THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Use of Systems Research Organizing Model

Inbox x

Brewer, Barbara B - (bbrewer) <bbrewer@email.arizona.edu>

Jun 10 ☆

to me ▾

Dear Colleen,

Sorry for the long response time, but I only received your request to use my model today. The University of Arizona is in Tucson, not Tempe. I'm not quite sure how your letter was forwarded to me, but it appears that a kind soul at Arizona State University corrected the address on the envelope, which is how it got to me.

Anyway, you have my permission to use the Systems Research Organizing Model as your theoretical framework. I would love to hear from you once you complete your project; feedback on how well the model fit for your project will be very helpful.

Best regards in completion of your project.

Barbara

Barbara B. Brewer, PhD, RN, MALS, MBA, FAAN

Associate Professor

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bbrewer@email.arizona.edu

APPENDIX C

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD APPROVAL FROM
KAISER PERMANENTE

InterOffice Memorandum

July 11, 2014

To: Colleen Bogdanich GNP-BC, MSN,
CCD
27107 Tourney Road
Santa Clarita , CA 91355

Re: Intravenous Osteoporosis Medication Adherence

Dear Ms. Bogdanich,

A designated reviewer on the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) reviewed your submission and determined that this is not human subjects research as defined by 45 CFR 46.102 (d) and (f).

If you have any questions, please contact Marcela Sanchez at 626-405-6124 (8-335-6124) or via email at Isabel.M.Sanchez@kp.org.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Armida Ayala".

Armida Ayala, MHA, PhD
Director of Human Research Subjects Protection
Office/Institutional Review Board (IRB)

APPENDIX D

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD APPROVAL FROM CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY LOS ANGELES

RE: IRB Intravenous Osteoporosis Medication Adherence is not a human subjects research

Inbox x

IRB <irb@calstatela.edu>

to me ▾

Aug 11 (7 days ago) ☆

Hi Ms. Bogdanich,

I received your documents where Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) IRB determined that Intravenous Osteoporosis Medication Adherence is not a human subjects research.

No further action is necessary.

Thank you,

Elia

From: Colleen Bogdanich [mailto:cdbogdanich@csu.fullerton.edu]

Sent: Friday, July 25, 2014 8:56 AM

To: Amaro, Elia

Subject: IRB

I am a Doctor of Nursing Practice student with my home campus being CSULA. I recently submitted my application for a QA/QI study through Kaiser Permanente and it was found not to be a human research study. Per our meeting last semester you advised the students that we may not need to resubmit to CSULA. attached is the copy of my application and the letter that is is not a human research study. Please let me know what my next steps are.

Sincerely,
Colleen Bogdanich